

PHYSIOLOGY OF BLOOD CELLULAR ELEMENTS**Marupova Malikabanu Ikhtiyarovna**
student**Tashkent State Medical University,**
Kamalova Zilola Mirsabitovna
assistant**Department of Pharmacology, Normal and Pathological Physiology,**
Tashkent State Medical University.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17978168>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 15th December 2025Accepted: 16th December 2025Online: 17th December 2025**KEYWORDS**

formed elements of blood, erythrocytes, leukocytes, platelets, erythropoiesis, leukopoiesis, hemostasis, homeostasis, blood physiology, cellular elements

ABSTRACT

This article examines the physiological characteristics of blood formed elements, their structure, functions, life cycle, and role in maintaining the body's homeostasis. Emphasis is placed on the regulation of erythropoiesis, leukopoiesis, and thrombopoiesis, as well as the relationship between cellular elements and plasma factors in respiratory, protective, and hemostatic functions.

Blood cells are cellular components that are responsible for various physiological functions. The three main types of formed elements in the blood are red blood cells, white blood cells and platelets.

These formed elements are suspended in plasma, the liquid component of blood that contains water, electrolytes, proteins, hormones and waste products. The production of red blood cells, platelets and white blood cells, known as hematopoiesis, occurs in the bone marrow.

Hematopoietic stem cells differentiate into specific blood cells under the influence of various growth factors and signaling molecules. The balance and regulation of these formed elements are critical to maintaining homeostasis and supporting the physiological functions of the body.

Any abnormalities in the number, structure or function of red blood cells, platelets and white blood cells can have serious health consequences and may indicate a variety of diseases, including anemia, leukemia, bleeding disorders and immune system disorders.

The formation of blood cells is called hematopoiesis, or hematopoiesis. This process is carried out in various hematopoietic organs. The bone marrow produces red blood cells, neutrophils, eosinophils and basophils. Lymphocytes form in the spleen and lymph nodes.

The formation of monocytes occurs in the bone marrow and in the reticular cells of the liver, spleen and lymph nodes. Platelets are produced in the red bone marrow and spleen.

The physiology of the formed elements of blood is one of the central sections of modern hematology and general physiology, since it is the cellular elements of the blood that provide the main vital functions of the body - transport, respiratory, protective, regulatory and hemostatic.

Blood, as a special tissue of the internal environment, acts as a universal link between all systems of the body, maintaining the constancy of its internal environment (homeostasis). Formed elements - red blood cells, leukocytes and platelets - make up about 45% total blood volume, and their physiological state and interaction with plasma components determine the body's resistance to stress and ability to adapt. Red blood cells, being the most numerous elements of blood, make up approximately 99% of all cells in the bloodstream.

Their main function is to transfer oxygen from the lungs to the tissues and carbon dioxide in the opposite direction, which is ensured by the presence of a specific protein - hemoglobin.

Each red blood cell is capable of binding up to a billion oxygen molecules, and the total surface of all red blood cells in an adult reaches 4000 m², which is approximately 2000 times the area of the skin. Thus, the physiological activity of red blood cells directly determines the efficiency of the respiratory function of the blood.

Leukocytes, making up less than 1% of blood volume, have an exceptional diversity of morphological and functional forms. They are the main component of immune defense, taking part in phagocytosis, antibody production, cytokine synthesis and regulation of inflammatory reactions.

The complexity of the leukocyte system lies in the high differentiation of cells - from neutrophils and lymphocytes to eosinophils, basophils and monocytes, each of which performs a strictly specialized function.

Hematopoiesis, or hematopoiesis, is a dynamic process that occurs in the bone marrow, where mature blood cells are formed from stem cells under the influence of specific growth factors and hormones.

Erythropoiesis is regulated primarily by the hormone erythropoietin, produced by the kidneys when the oxygen level in the blood decreases. Leukopoiesis is controlled by a system of cytokines, including interleukins and colony-stimulating factors, while thrombocytopoiesis is regulated by thrombopoietin and megakaryocyte growth factors.

The physiological dynamics of formed elements reflects the state of the body's adaptive capabilities. Thus, during physical activity or hypoxia, a compensatory increase in erythropoiesis occurs, ensuring an improvement in the oxygen capacity of the blood.

During infections and inflammatory processes, leukopoiesis is activated, the content of neutrophils and lymphocytes increases. An important aspect is maintaining a homeostatic balance between the processes of formation and destruction of blood cells.

Every day, a person produces about 200 billion red blood cells, 10 billion white blood cells and 400 billion platelets, which illustrates the enormous intensity of hematopoiesis. Violation of this balance can lead to pathological conditions - anemia, leukopenia, thrombocytopenia or, conversely, to cell hyperproliferation.

Modern research shows that the activity of hematopoietic processes is regulated not only by hormonal and biochemical factors, but also by neuroendocrine mechanisms.

The hypothalamic-pituitary axis is involved in the regulation of hematopoiesis through the influence of adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH), glucocorticoids and catecholamines, which alter the proliferation of progenitor cells in the bone marrow.

The role of the bone marrow microenvironment, which provides optimal conditions for cell maturation, deserves special attention. Stromal cells, macrophages and fibroblasts secrete biologically active substances that regulate the growth and differentiation of formed elements.

The study of the physiology of blood cells is of great practical importance. It underlies the diagnosis of diseases of the blood system, assessment of the functional state of the body and the development of methods for correcting hematopoietic disorders.

In modern conditions, this area is actively developing thanks to the achievements of cell biology, molecular genetics and bioengineering, which opens up prospects for the creation of artificial hematopoietic systems and gene therapy for blood diseases.

Thus, at the end of the literature review, it can be noted that the formed elements of blood - red blood cells, leukocytes and platelets - are highly specialized cellular structures that play a key role in maintaining the vital functions of the body.

Literature:

1. Guyton A. S., Hall J. E. Medical physiology. - M.: Logosphere, 2022. - 1340 p.
2. Schmidt R.F., Tevs G. Human physiology. - St. Petersburg: Peter, 2021. - 1024 p.
3. Sudakov K.V. Systemic mechanisms for regulating the functions of the human body. - M.: Nauka, 2020. - 480 p.
4. Kostyuchenko V. P. Hematopoiesis and blood physiology. - M.: GEOTAR-Media, 2023. - 398 p.
5. Fedorov A.V. Modern ideas about the regulation of hematopoiesis. - Kazan: KSMU, 2022. - 214 p.
6. Guyton A. C., Hall J. E. Textbook of Medical Physiology. — 15th ed. — Philadelphia: Elsevier, 2022. — 1200 p.
7. Tortora G. J., Derrickson B. Principles of Anatomy and Physiology. — 16th ed. — Wiley, 2023. — 1296 p.
8. Mohrman D. E., Heller L. J. Cardiovascular and Blood Physiology. — McGraw-Hill, 2022. — 384 p.
9. Hoffman R. Hematology: Basic Principles and Practice. — 8th ed. — Philadelphia: Elsevier, 2023. — 2700 p.
10. Kaushansky K. Growth Factors and Hematopoiesis. — New York: Springer, 2021. — 442 p.
11. Iolascon A., Andolfo I. Red Cell Membrane Disorders and Physiology. — Blood Rev., 2023, Vol. 57, 101023.
12. Papayannopoulou T. Mechanisms of Erythropoiesis: From Stem Cell to Mature Red Cell. — Blood, 2022, Vol. 140, No. 4, p. 345–358.
13. Qian H., Buza-Vidas N. Stem Cell Niche and Hematopoietic Regulation. — Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell Biol., 2023, Vol. 24, No. 6, p. 389–403.
14. Nathan D. G., Orkin S. H. Hematology of Infancy and Childhood. — Elsevier, 2021. — 1680 p.
15. Pivkin I. V., Karniadakis G. E. RBC Biomechanics and Deformability Modeling. — Prog. Biophys. Mol. Biol., 2022, Vol. 170, p. 88–102.
16. Zorina A. V., Петрова Н. А. Возрастные изменения в системе гемопоэза человека. — Журнал физиологии, 2023. — №4. — С. 22–29.